

INFLUENCE OF THE CURING PROCESS ON THE MANUFACTURE OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES WITH EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

The present work studies the most adequate process for the manufacture of carbon/epoxy laminates with embedded optical fibres. The influence of the curing process on the final state of the laminate was studied. If the laminate were to suffer any damage there would be a considerable influence on the light transmission properties of the optical fibre. The embedded optical fibre can thus be considered to be a damage detection sensor for measuring the structural integrity of the laminate. The presence of the embedded optical fibre in the laminate was studied to determine its influence on the mechanical properties of the laminate. This study will allow us to determine the most adequate distribution of optical fibres in the laminate for the particular use to which it is destined.

KEYWORDS: carbon/epoxy laminate, embedded optical fibre, damage detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in the different fields of engineering is becoming more extensive every day. The reason for its success is due fundamentally to the properties that make them different from other conventional materials. Their high strenght to weight ratio, the ease of molding into complex shapes, and resistance to fatigue and corrosion make them particularly attractive for certain uses.

However, due to their particular properties, damages induced by low energy impacts cannot be detected by visual inspection. Lengthy procedures using X-rays and C-scan ultrasound techniques are required to detect these damages. For this reason it has become necessary to develop a method for assessing the integrity of the composite material in a quick and safe manner.

Over the last few years, a great amount of work has been devoted to detect this type of damage with the use of embedded optical fibres in composite materials [1, 2]. Also there have been works guided to determine the stress state of composite materials that have embedded optical fibres [3]. Diverse methods have been used, from the determination of the transmission integrity of the fibre

as a measure of damage [4, 5], to the use of high sensitivity interferometry techniques capable of measuring material deformation [6]. Transmission integrity systems are more widely used in practice.

We decided to use a transmission integrity system and considered what effect would be produced on the quality of the laminate by the presence of the optical fibre. Since the optical fibre diameter varies from 100 to 200 microns and the reinforcement fibre diameter varies from 8 to 20 microns, the optical fibres create a distortion that affects the quality of the laminate. Existing works have measured the loss of laminate properties due to the presence of optical fibres [7, 8]. Also, the stress imposed on the optical fibre by the laminate manufacture process has to be taken into account. As we shall demonstrate, the use of a particular curing method induces a greater or lesser effect on the fibre, even reaching the complete fracture of the fibre so that the transmission of light is not possible.

The present study has undertaken the problem from two perspectives. On one hand, we pretend to see the influence that the manufacture process has on the final state of the optical fibre by measuring its light transmission properties. On the other hand, we pretend to see the influence that the optical fibre has on the characteristics of the laminate by studying their microstructural characterization, the fibre/resin distribution, the presence of pores, the distribution of resin-rich zones and other defects.

2. EXPERIMENTS

Two procedures were selected for the manufacture of composite materials that yield laminates of different characteristics. The first procedure was manufacture with the autoclave curing process in order to obtain high quality laminates for the aircraft industry. We used the Hercules Aerospace IM7/8552 prepreg system. The curing cycle was set to two and a half hours at a pressure of 3 bar.

The second procedure consisted of placing the laminate in a vacuum and curing it in an oven. This yields a laminate of similar characteristics to that available in industry and used in more conventional applications. We used HEXCEL's EPO-685 epoxy resin and HEXCEL's taffeta of 193 g/m². The manufacturer's recommended curing cycle was used, reaching a maximum temperature of 100C. A vacuum of approximately 1 bar was produced by a vacuum pump.

The optical fibres were placed by hand in different positions between the layers of the laminate. In order to study the influence of optical fibre orientation with respect to the reinforcement fibres, some optical fibres were placed in parallel to, and others were placed perpendicular to the reinforcement fibres, as shown in Table 1. The distance between optical fibres placed in a layer was of 2 cm for the autoclave process and 1 cm for the vacuum process.

The chosen optical fibres were Corning's multimode with a 50 micron nuclei, a 125 micron external diameter and a numerical aperture of 0.21. The optical fibres were used after immersion in trichloromethane to remove their protective coating. These optical fibres were used as such and also after immersion in ammonia difluoride [5]. Optical fibres with their silicone protective coating left intact were also used.

In the unidirectional composite material, made of 12 layers, the optical fibres were placed between the 3rd and 4th layers or between the 9th and 10th layers. One laminate had optical fibres embedded between the 10th and 11th layers. In the taffeta composite material, made of 6 layers, the optical fibres were placed between the 3rd and 4th layer or on the two external layers.

Table 1. Placement of the optical fibres in the laminates under test.

LAMINATE	OPTIC Fibre	ORIENTATION	PLACEMENT
1	Without coating	Parallel	between 3-4 layer
2	Without coating	Perpendicular	between 10-11 layer
3	NH ₄ HF ₂ Treatment	Parallel	between 3-4 layer
4	NH ₄ HF ₂ Treatment	Perpendicular	between 9-10 layer
5	With coating	Parallel	between 9-10 layer
6	With coating	Perpendicular	between 9-10 layer
7	Without coating	Taffeta material	between 3-4 layer
8	Without coating	Taffeta material	between 2-3 & 4-5 layer
9	Without coating	Taffeta material	between 1-2 & 5-6 layer
10	NH ₄ HF ₂ Treatment	Taffeta material	between 3-4 layer

3. INFLUENCE OF THE OPTICAL FIBRES ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LAMINATE

The placement of 125 microns optical fibres produce unavoidable effects on the prepreg since it displaces the 8 microns reinforcement fibres. The curing of the laminates with embedded optical fibres produces this displacement which is more pronounced when the optical fibres are perpendicular to the prepreg. The diameter of the optical fibres is very close in size to the thickness of a layer of prepreg (120 to 140 microns), as can be seen in Figure 1. This displacement of the reinforcement fibres creates lenticularly shaped zones rich in resin and centered around the optical fibre, specially in laminates where the optical fibre is placed transversally to the reinforcement fibres.

Figure 1. Transverse cross-section of the optical fibre, corresponding to laminate number 2. Clear background, X100 magnification.

Because of this, local elastic deformations are produced that give rise to stress concentrators and matrix deformations which may produce a premature failure of the composite material [7].

An additional problem resulting from these zones which are rich in resin is the accumulation of air in the form of numerous pores, as seen in Figure 1, whose diameter is similar to that of the

optical fibre. These pores lessen the quality of the composite material and introduce important geometric defects in the laminate.

Figure 2. Transverse cross-section of the optical fibre with protective coating, corresponding to laminate number 6. Clear background, X100 magnification.

When optical fibres with their silicone protective coating left intact are used, as seen in Figure 2 corresponding to laminate number 6, the zones which are rich in resin become larger, with an increase of their effect on the mechanical properties of the laminate. An analysis of the normalized cross-section stress [9] indicates a minimum is present between the fibre and its protective coating, which explains the type of tensile test fracture observed with this laminate where the optical fibre is seen to have suffered an important extraction, as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of a tensile test fracture at 90 degrees to laminate number 6. X350 magnification.

The effect of the zone which is rich in matrix diminishes with the angle between the optical fibre and the adjacent layers [10]. This effect becomes negligible at a point where the optical fibre is

parallel to the reinforcement fibres. Even so, a more favorable placement of the optical fibre can be appreciated precisely between the two layers, which can produce a displacement of the reinforcement fibres on the central zone of the optical fibre, as can be seen in Figure 4. This displacement can produce a zone which is rich in resin such as that observed in the tensile test fracture at 90 degrees, which in almost every case broke by the optical fibre as can be seen on Figure 5.

Figure 4. Detail of the distribution of reinforcement fibres around the optical fibre of laminate number 3. Clear background, X400 magnification.

Figure 5. Superficial aspect of the tensile test fracture at 90 degrees to laminate number 3, showing a zone which is rich in resin. X150 magnification.

Tensile tests were made at 0 and 90 degrees in order to verify the effect on the mechanical properties of the laminate and the optical fibre as reported by Measures et al. [11] and Jensen et al. [7] among others who found a 10% reduction under tensile loading and a 20% reduction under compressive loading [8]. Tests performed with samples made of unidirectional laminates with embedded optical fibres yielded the same values as test performed with the same laminates but without optical fibres. The elastic modulus for tests at 0 degrees was found to be between 141 and 158 GPa; for tests at 90 degrees it was found to be between 8.1 and 9.1 GPa. The fracture strength was found to be between 2100 and 2400 MPa for tests at 0 degrees and between 45 and 69 MPa

for tests at 90 degrees, concluding that the optical fibres had only a minor influence.

4. EFFECT OF COMPOSITE DISTRIBUTION ON THE OPTICAL FIBRE

Although reinforcement fibre and matrix distribution defects were caused by the embedded optical fibres, no significant effect was observed on the mechanical properties of the composite material and therefore its structural integrity is not compromised. The same cannot be said about the effect that the composite material has on the optical fibre.

The reason for embedding optical fibres in a composite material is to use them as sensors and to be able to transmit light through them without losses, as observed in the transmission micrographs of Figure 6, where the nucleus or core of the optical fibre can be clearly differentiated from the clad, and partial deterioration of the protective coating as seen in Figure 6b.

Figure 6. Transmission micrograph of embedded optical fibres placed in parallel to the reinforcement fibres. a) Fibre of laminate number 3 in perfect state. b) Fibre of laminate number 5 with protective coating. X200 magnification.

Figure 7. Cracks formed on optical fibres that were embedded perpendicularly to the reinforcement fibres. a) Laminate number 2. b) Laminate number 4. X400 magnification.

However, the pressure formed during the curing process of the composite material, basically in the autoclave process, accumulate stresses on the optical fibre which, if placed perpendicularly to the

reinforcement fibres, cause it to deteriorate as seen in Figure 7. Longitudinal cracks are produced on almost all fibres although light transmission is not impaired completely.

The fracture of laminates in which optical fibres without their protective coating were embedded is parallel to the curing stresses, corresponding with the distribution of stresses on the optical fibre. However, when the protective silicone coating was left intact, it deformed elastically such that the produced fracture was perpendicular to the stress.

When the laminates in which the optical fibre was parallel to the reinforcement fibres were analyzed, we only found significant deterioration in laminate number 5, where the protective coating was left intact such that it acted as a stress distribution elastic element, as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Fracture of laminate number 5, embedded with optical fibres in which the protective coating was left intact. Clear background. X200 magnification.

As it becomes patent from the different micrographs, the biggest problem is to maintain the integrity of the optical fibres during the curing process of the composite material fundamentally for two reasons: the first is due to the fragility of the optical fibre, specially when without its protective coating which makes it difficult to handle and can produce pores, by absorbed air in the laminate; the second is due to the pressures produced during the curing of processes used to obtain an aircraft quality laminate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the embedding of optical fibres in laminates whether in parallel or perpendicular to the reinforcement fibres maintains the integrity of the structures since no appreciable diminution of its mechanical characteristics are observed, and in no case higher than 20%. However, the most important problem found stems from the integrity of the optical fibres which deteriorate in an important manner during the curing process of the composite material, which takes us to continue the investigation with:

- matrices of larger flow that allow lower pressures in the process, maintaining the adequate mechanical characteristics for the application of the laminate.
- integration of the optical fibre within the prepreg to avoid the displacement of the

reinforcement fibres and the stress concentration it produces on the optical fibre, because in this case it would be a substitution of reinforcement fibres with optical fibres.

- optical fibre diameter reduction to about 35 to 50 microns without protective coating to allow for a better integration in the reinforcement.

With these the noticeable degradation of the optical fibre properties shall be prevented, which otherwise show an excellent compatibility with the carbon/epoxy laminate materials.

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